

SCHOOL HEADS TRANSFORMATIONAL LEADERSHIP PRACTICES, TEACHERS' MORALE, AND PERFORMANCE

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School Heads Transformational Leadership Practices, Teachers' Morale, and Performance

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to determine the school heads transformational leadership practices, teachers' morale, and performance. Survey data were gathered from 10 school heads and 150 teachers from public elementary schools of Division of Lanao del Sur. The findings revealed that both the teachers and school heads respondents rated "high" the leadership practices of the school heads, in terms of transformational leadership practices. However, they tend to show high morale when it comes to teacher Rapport with the school head, satisfaction with teaching, rapport among teachers, teacher salary, teacher status, and it shows very high in terms of curriculum issues. Moreover, the result of the Performance Appraisal System for Teachers (PAST) revealed that most teachers' respondents have very high satisfactory performance measured in terms of instructional competence, professional and personal characteristics, punctuality and attendance. However, variables, namely moral satisfaction, teachers' transformational leadership, and school heads' transformational leadership, have no direct association with their PAST. Based on the finding, this study concludes that the elementary school teachers' Performance appraisal has a significant relationship to the teachers' transformational leadership assessment and teachers' morale satisfaction in contrast, it has no significant relationship to school heads transformational leadership. Teachers' morale satisfaction is the best predictor of teachers' performance, which implies that once teachers are satisfied with their personal and professional engagement in the school, their performance would be better.

Keywords: *headship, satisfaction, confidence, transmuted, faculty*

Introduction

One of the basic issues and concerns for all organizations and institutions like the school was on the leadership practice used by their administrators. The role of the school head in relation to school administration is a topic that has always been subject to evaluation for the success of the school. Quality leadership practices performed by the school heads were considered as the most important tools for achieving and determining the excellence and success of a school.

Leadership practices are the manner and approach of providing direction, implementing plans, and motivating people. Leaders must be knowledge synthesizers. They must bring intelligence to the leadership enterprise. They need to know about past events, understand the realities of the present, and have a vision of the future. They must not be experts in their chosen field but be familiar with many other areas as well (K. Blanchard, 2011). Systems thinkers are consciously aware that everything is connected to everything else. The obvious problems plaguing an organization may be symptoms rather than root causes. A system approach to change allows leaders to logically analyze the dimensions of the problems (NJ: Prentice Hall, 2007). According to Squires (2001), leaders were concerned with the spiritual aspect of their work, that is, they have followers who deeply believe in them and they possess a power in the organization.

This research was focused on the context of the school heads' behaviors and how those behaviors translate to teachers, pupils and staff of the school. It was the researcher's belief that if a school leader was able to practice a positive leadership style, it was in turn help bring a positive learning climate to the school. Teachers was feel more comfortable and thus give a positive result to the educative process.

Research Questions

This study focused on the context of the school heads' transformational leadership practices and teacher's morale as correlates to teachers' performance.

1. What is the assessment of the teacher respondents on school heads transformational leadership practices of the administrators in terms of:
 - 1.1. Modeling the Way;
 - 1.2. Inspiring a Shared Vision;
 - 1.3. Challenging the Process;
 - 1.4. Enabling Others to Act;
 - 1.5. Encouraging the Heart?
2. What is the assessment of the school head respondents on school heads transformational leadership practices of the administrators in terms of:
 - 2.1. Modeling the Way;
 - 2.2. Inspiring a Shared Vision;
 - 2.3. Challenging the Process;

- 2.4. Enabling Others to Act;
- 2.5. Encouraging the Heart?
3. What is the teacher respondents assessment on their morale along the following factors:
 - 3.1. Teacher Rapport with School Head;
 - 3.2. Satisfaction with Teaching;
 - 3.3. Rapport among Teachers;
 - 3.4. Teacher Salary;
 - 3.5. Teacher Load;
 - 3.6. Curriculum Issues;
 - 3.7. Teacher Status;
 - 3.8. School Facilities and Services?
4. What is the level of performance of teachers in terms of:
 - 4.1. Instructional Competence;
 - 4.2. Professional and Personal Characteristics;
 - 4.3. Punctuality and Attendance?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the school heads' transformational leadership practices, teachers morale, and teachers' performance?
6. Which variables predict teachers' performance?

Methodology

Research Design

This research utilized descriptive-correlational research design was used since the study deals with the determining the school heads' leadership practices in relation to teachers' morale and teachers' performance. They will ask specific questions and details about their school heads, teaching in general, curriculum issues, and questions dealing with the school community. They survey will design to be self-administer. The Purdue Teacher Opinionnaire was chosen to measure the factors contributing to teachers' morale. This instrument used a Likert-type scale to collect and measure each variable of the research. The Leadership Practices Inventory measures five transformational leadership practices that best support great accomplishments in every school. The respondents will be the 10 school administrators and 150 teachers in the Division of Lanao del Sur employed for the year 2019-2020.

Respondents

These subjects of the study were the ten (10) public elementary school heads and one hundred fifty (150) teachers from Ganassi District, Madamba District, Madalum District, Bacolod District, Tugaya District, and Balindong District of the Division of Lanao del Sur.

These school heads and teachers were currently employed during school year 2019-2020. I choose the nearest districts. Table 1 shows the distribution of the respondents according to districts and schools. The data was taken from the Form 3, Report of Attendance and Enrolment in the Office of the Public Schools District Supervisor.

Table 1. *Respondents of the Study*

<i>District</i>	<i>Number Of Participants</i>
Pualas District	20
Central Ganassi District	11
Upper Madamba District	11
Lower Madamba District	16
South Madalum	12
East Tugaya	21
Central Tugaya	13
Bacolod District	12
Balindong I	24
Balindong II	21
Total Number Of Participants	160

Instrument

This study used a three-part questionnaire. The first was the survey instrument on Leadership Practices Inventory (LPI 9Kouzes & Posner, 1993). The LPI was designed to measure leadership qualities. It consists of two components: The Leadership Practices Inventory-Self and Leadership Practices Inventory-Observer. The Leadership Practices Inventory-Observer is a 30-item Likert-scale questionnaire measuring the five areas of challenging the process, inspiring a shared vision, enabling others to act, modelling the way, and encouraging the heart. A higher value represented greater use of leadership behaviour: one- rarely or very seldom do what is described, two – once in a while do what is described, three – sometimes do what is described, four – fairly often do what is described, and five – frequently or almost always do what is describe in the statement.

Procedure

In gathering the data for the study, the investigator wrote a letter of consent from the Dean of the School of Graduate Studies for approval by the Vice President of Research, Publication and Extension. Additionally, another letter was addressed to the President of Liceo de Cagayan University through the Vice President of Human Resource Development for approval to conduct the study. Then, the researcher was given the questionnaires to the regular employee of the University. After a week, the questionnaires were retrieved, and the data were sent to the statistician for analysis and interpretation of data.

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation were used to describe the indicators and variables of the study. Problems 1, 2, and 3 utilized the mean and standard deviation.

Problem 4 and 5 used the Pearson *r* Analyses was used to determine the significant relationship between teachers' performance, transformational leadership practices of school heads assessed by teachers, transformational leadership assessment of school heads, and morale satisfaction of teachers. Problem 6 used and Multiple Regression Analyses was used to Predict Teachers' Performance weather influenced by other factors (<0.5 alpha level) among independent variables best predict teachers' performance.

Results and Discussion

The researcher has collected the following data using three sets of questionnaires, each with a diverse purpose: to measure leadership qualities. It consists of two components: The Leadership Practices Inventory-Self and Leadership Practices Inventory-Observer. The Leadership Practices Inventory-Observer is a 30-item Likert-scale questionnaire measuring the five areas of challenging the process, inspiring a shared vision, enabling others to act, modelling the way, and encouraging the heart. The overall number of participants was one hundred sixty (160). The participants were from different randomly selected districts of Division of Lanao del Sur, particularly the regular school heads and teachers for one year and more. The purposive sampling procedure was utilized in getting the sample of the study as it purposefully needed rank-and-file employees, identities of the employees, as well as the schools where they are currently employed, were not recorded for confidentiality purposes; however, a letter of consent, which given to each participant to read before agreeing to answer the survey questionnaire.

Problem 1. What is the assessment of the teacher respondents on school head transformational leadership practices of the administrators in terms of modeling the way, inspiring a shared vision, challenging the process, enabling others to act, and encouraging the heart?

Table 1. *Teachers Assessment on the School Head Transformational Leadership Practices of the Administrators in terms of Modeling the way, Inspiring Shared Vision, Challenging the Process, Enabling Others to Act, and Encouraging the Heart*

<i>Modeling the Way</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1 Sets a personal example of what he/she expect of others.	4.6	.413	Always	Very High
2 Talks about future trends that will influence how our work gets done.	4.11	.867	Always	Very High
6 Spends time and energy making certain that the people he/she works with adhere to the principals and standards we have agreed on.	3.84	.513	Often	High
7 Describes a compelling image of what our future could be like.	4.04	.967	Always	Very High
11 Follows through on the promises and commitments that he/she make.	4.09	.313	Always	Very High
16 Asks for feedback on how his/her actions affect other people's performance.	2.62	.467	Always	Very High
21 Builds consensus around a common set of values for running our organization.	4.32	.713	Often	High
26 Is clear about his/her philosophy of leadership.	4.14	.967	Always	Very High
Overall	3.97	0.65	Often	High
<i>Inspiring a Shared Vision</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
12 Appeals to others to share an exciting dream of the future.	4.8	.546	Always	Very High
17 Shows others how their long-term interests can be realized by enlisting in a common vision.	4	.476	Often	High
22 Paints the "big picture" of what we aspire to accomplish.	3.4	.656	Often	High
27 Speaks with a genuine conviction about the higher meaning and purpose of our work.	4.7	.056	Always	High
Overall	4.2	0.67	Often	High
<i>Challenging the process.</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
3 Seeks out challenging opportunities that test his/her own skills and abilities.	4.13	.713	Often	High
8 Challenges people to try out new and innovative ways to do their work.	4.22	.667	Often	High
13 Searches outside the formal boundaries of his/her organization for innovative ways to improve what we do.	4.32	.813	Always	Very High

23 Makes certain that we set achievable goals, make concrete plans, and establish measurable milestones for the projects and programs that we work on.	4.17	.867	Often	High
28 Experiments and take risks, even when there is a chance of failure.	4.36	.613	Often	High
Overall	4.24	0.73	Often	High
Enabling Others to Act				
	Mean	SD	Verbal Description	Interpretation
4 Develops cooperative relationships among the people he/she works with.	4.72	.213	Often	High
9 Actively listens to diverse points of view.	4.65	.067	Often	High
14 Treats others with dignity and respect.	3.85	0.453	Often	High
19 Supports the decisions that people make on their own.	4.48	0.563	Often	High
24 Gives people a great deal of freedom and choice in deciding how to do their work.	4.54	0.675	Often	High
29 Ensures that people grow in their jobs by learning new skills and developing themselves.	4.6	.0876	Always	Very High
Overall	4.47	0.34	Often	High
Encouraging the Heart				
	Mean	SD	Verbal Description	Interpretation
5 Praises people for a job well done.	4.36	0.568	Often	High
10 Makes it a point to let people know about his/her confidence in their abilities.	4.2	0.876	Often	High
15 Makes sure that people are creatively rewarded for their contributions to the success of our projects.	4.24	.0897	Often	High
20 Publicly recognizes that people who exemplify commitment to shared values.	4.3	0.785	Often	High
25 Finds ways to celebrate accomplishments.	4.0	0.745	Often	High
30 Gives the members of the team lots of appreciation and support for their contribution.	4.29	0.878	Often	High
Overall	4.23	0.65	Often	High

Table 2. Summary of Assessment of the Teacher Respondents on School Head Transformational Leadership Practices of the Administrators in terms of Modeling The Way, Inspiring a Shared Vision, Challenging the Process, Enabling Others to Act, and Encouraging the Heart

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description	Interpretation
Modeling the Way	3.97	0.65	Often	High
Inspiring a Shared Vision	4.2	0.67	Often	High
Challenging the Process	4.24	0.73	Often	High
Enabling Others to Act	4.47	0.34	Often	High
Encouraging the Heart	4.23	0.65	Often	High
Overall	4.22	0.608	Often	High

Legend: 4.50-5.00, Always, Very High; 3.50-4.49, Often, High; 2.50-3.49, Sometimes, Moderate; 1.50-2.49, Seldom, Low; 1.00-1.49, Never, Very Low

Table 2 presents the summary of assessment of the teacher respondents on school head transformational leadership practices of the administrators in terms of modeling the way, inspiring a shared vision, challenging the process, enabling others to act, and encouraging the heart. As shown in the table, the teachers obtained the highest assessment of their school head’s transformational leadership in enabling others to act with a mean of 4.47, followed by challenging the process with a mean of 4.24, encouraging the heart with a mean of 4.23, inspiring a shared vision with a mean of 4.2, and the modeling the way with a mean of 3.97. The overall mean is 4.22 which can be inferred that the teachers have high belief of their school heads as transformational leaders in the school and in the community.

House (2006), as cited by Northouse, (2007) discussed a charismatic theory of leadership. He stated charismatic leaders are dominant, have a desire to influence, are confident, and have strong values. These charismatic leaders exhibit the behaviors of role modeling, confidence, goal articulation, high expectations, confidence, and motivation. As a result of these behaviors, subordinates portray trust in the leaders’ ideology, believe they are similar to the leader, and unilaterally accept the leaders’ goals. Subordinates also exhibit affection towards the leader, obedience, emotional involvement, heightened goals, and increased confidence.

Leadership, as defined by Burns (2008), is a link between the leader and subordinates. The researcher differentiated between two types of leadership. The two types of leadership are transactional and transformational. Transactional leadership refers to everyday exchanges that occur between leaders and subordinates

Transformational leadership refers to the process in which the leader attempts to engage and create a connection with subordinates; thus, raising the level of motivation and morality for both. Bass (2005) and Bass and Avolio (2004) suggested transactional and transformational leadership are not mutually exclusive but exist on a continuum.

Bennis and Nanus (2005) identified four methods by which organizations were transformed by leaders. Transformational leaders have a clear vision, are social architects, create trust, and use creative deployment. Kouzes and Posner (2007) labeled five exemplary practices of leadership. The researchers interviewed 1,300 leaders and managers regarding their best leadership experiences. The five exemplary practices identified are model the way, inspire a shared vision, challenge the process, enable others to act, and encourage

the heart. The important underlying principles related to modeling the way include clarifying values and setting the example.

Leech and Fulton (2008) performed a correlational study to determine the relationship between teachers' perceptions of the level of shared decision making practice in their schools and their perceptions of the leadership behaviors of their principals. The sample consisted of 646 participants from 26 schools in a large urban public school system.

Problem 2. What is the assessment of the school heads on transformational leadership practices in terms of, Modeling the Way, Inspiring a Shared Vision, Challenging the Process, Enabling Others to Act, and Encouraging the Heart

Table 3. School Heads' Assessment on the School head Transformational Leadership Practices of the Administrators in terms of Modeling The Way, Inspiring Shared Vision, Challenging the Process, Enabling Others to Act, and Encouraging the Heart

Modeling the Way	Mean	SD	Verbal Description	Interpretation
1 Sets a personal example of what he/she expect of others.	4.8	0.665	Always	Very High
2 Talks about future trends that will influence how our work gets done.	4.7	0.887	Always	Very High
6 Spends time and energy making certain that the people he/she works with adhere to the principals and standards we have agreed on.	4.4	0.556	Often	High
7 Describes a compelling image of what our future could be like.	4.9	0.876	Always	Very High
11 Follows through on the promises and commitments that he/she make.	4.6	0.778	Always	Very High
16 Asks for feedback on how his/her actions affect other people's performance.	4.7	0.556	Always	Very High
21 Builds consensus around a common set of values for running our organization.	4.3	0.667	Often	High
26 Is clear about his/her philosophy of leadership.	5	0.886	Always	Very High
Overall	4.6	.361	Often	High
Inspiring a Shared Vision	Mean	SD	Verbal Description	Interpretation
12 Appeals to others to share an exciting dream of the future.	4.9	0.670	Always	Very High
17 Shows others how their long-term interests can be realized by enlisting in a common vision.	3.9	0.788	Often	High
22 Paints the "big picture" of what we aspire to accomplish.	4.4	0.866	Often	High
27 Speaks with a genuine conviction about the higher meaning and purpose of our work.	4.6	0.655	Always	High
Overall	4.45	.401	Often	High
Challenging the Process	Mean	SD	Verbal Description	Interpretation
3 Seeks out challenging opportunities that test his/her own skills and abilities.	4.4	.687	Often	High
8 Challenges people to try out new and innovative ways to do their work.	4.3	0.773	Often	High
13 Searches outside the formal boundaries of his/her organization for innovative ways to improve what we do.	4.2	0.884	Always	Very High
23 Makes certain that we set achievable goals, make concrete plans, and establish measurable milestones for the projects and programs that we work on.	3.9	0.345	Often	High
28 Experiments and take risks, even when there is a chance of failure.	4.1	0.668	Often	High
Overall	4.18	.205	Often	High
Enabling Others to Act	Mean	SD	Verbal Description	Interpretation
4 Develops cooperative relationships among the people he/she works with.	4.1	.613	Often	High
9 Actively listens to diverse points of view.	4.3	.967	Often	High
14 Treats others with dignity and respect.	4.4	.413	Often	High
19 Supports the decisions that people make on their own.	4.3	.867	Often	High
24 Gives people a great deal of freedom and choice in deciding how to do their work.	4.3	.613	Often	High
29 Ensures that people grow in their jobs by learning new skills and developing themselves.	4.5	.967	Always	Very High
Overall	4.31	.136	Often	High
Encouraging the Heart	Mean	SD	Verbal Description	Interpretation
5 Praises people for a job well done.	4.2	.236	Often	High
10 Makes it a point to let people know about his/her confidence in their abilities.	4.3	.640	Often	High
15 Makes sure that people are creatively rewarded for their contributions to the success of our projects.	4.2	.720	Often	High
20 Publicly recognizes that people who exemplify commitment to shared values.	4.4	.213	Often	High
25 Finds ways to celebrate accomplishments.	4.1	.067	Often	High
30 Gives the members of the team lots of appreciation and support for their contribution.	4.1	.513	Often	High
Overall	4.21	.675	Often	High

Table 4. Summary of Assessment of the School Heads on Transformational Leadership Practices of the Administrators in terms of Modeling The Way, Inspiring a Shared Vision, Challenging the Process, Enabling Others to Act, and Encouraging the Heart

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description	Interpretation
Modeling the Way	4.6	.361	Often	High
Inspiring a Shared Vision	4.45	.401	Often	High
Challenging the Process	4.18	.205	Often	High
Enabling Others to Act	4.31	.136	Often	High
Encouraging the Heart	4.21	.675	Often	High
Overall	4.35	.361	Often	High

Legend: 4.50-5.00, Always, Very High; 3.50-4.49, Often, High; 2.50-3.49, Sometimes, Moderate; 1.50-2.49, Seldom, Low; 1.00-1.49, Never, Very Low

Table 4 presents the summary of assessment of the school heads on transformational leadership practices of the administrators in terms of modeling the way, inspiring a shared vision, challenging the process, enabling others to act, and encouraging the heart. As depicted in the table, the school heads have assessed themselves higher in modeling the way with a mean of 4.6, followed by inspiring a shared vision with a mean of 4.45, enabling others to act with a mean of 4.31, encouraging the heart with a mean of 4.21, and challenging the process with a lowest mean of 4.18. The overall mean is 4.35 which can be interpreted that the school heads have higher level of transformational leadership.

Jantzi and Leithwood (2005) examined principals’ transformational leadership performance as rated by teachers’ overall perception. Six individual leadership dimensions were measured. The dimensions included identifying and articulating a vision, fostering the acceptance of group goals, providing individualized support, providing intellectual stimulation, serving as an exemplary model, and demonstrating high expectations for performance. The sample included teachers in British Columbia, Canada who worked in schools that participated in a 5-year study of policy implementation.

The relationship between elementary school principals’ transformational leadership behaviors and the presence of social-organizational factors within schools was researched by Evans (2006). Shared goals, teacher collaboration, teacher learning, teacher certainty, and teacher commitment were the social-organizational factors examined. Teachers and principals were administered the Multi-factor Leadership Questionnaire and the School Organizational Factors Questionnaire. The researcher found principals deemed high in transformational leadership led schools higher in the social-organizational factors. The variables of principals’ years of service and school staff size were found to be significant indicators of a principal’s transformational leadership.

Day (2000) discussed what attributes make an effective school principal. The author reviewed a 1998 study performed in the United Kingdom. Twelve headmasters were studied from schools of different geographic regions, different sizes, different operational phases, and different socio-cultural settings. A research team visited each school for a three day observation period.

Leithwood and Steinbach (2003) examined total quality leadership as a tool toward effective leadership practices. They defined total quality leadership as encompassing expert thinking and transformational leadership. The sample included nine secondary school principals. Researcher methodology included a principal interview as well as a survey related to their teachers’ perceptions of their behavior in regards to the six dimensions of transformational leadership. The authors found that exhibiting transformational leadership qualities is not sufficient by itself to accomplish total quality leadership.

Leithwood (2003) also summarized the results of different research studies in direct relation to the three concepts of transformational leadership. General results included: transformational leadership had a positive direct and indirect impact on school restructuring initiatives, there was no longer a need to distinguish between transactional and transformational leadership, and contingent reward was a construct of transformational leadership.

Problem 3. How do the teacher respondents assess their morale satisfaction along with the following factors namely teacher rapport with school head, satisfaction with teaching, rapport among teachers, teacher salary, teacher load, curriculum issues, teacher status, and school facilities.

Table 5. Level of Morale Satisfaction of Teachers Along with the Following Factors Namely Teacher Rapport with School Head, Satisfaction with Teaching, Rapport Among Teachers, Teacher Salary, Teacher Load, Curriculum Issues, Teacher Status, and School Facilities

Teacher Rapport with School Head	Mean	SD	Verbal Description	Interpretation
1 The work of individual faculty members is appreciated and commended by our principal	3.56	.323	Strongly Agree	Very High
2 Teachers feel free to criticize administrative policy at faculty meetings called by our principal.	3.04	.964	Agree	High
3 Our principal shows favoritism in his relations with the teachers in our school.	2.82	.872	Agree	High
5 My principal makes a real effort to maintain close contact with the faculty.	2.96	.221	Agree	High
10 Our principal’s leadership in faculty meetings challenges and stimulates our professional growth.	2.59	.406	Agree	High

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27 My principal makes my work easier and more pleasant.	2.89	.723	Agree	High
31 My school principal understands and recognizes good teaching procedures.	3.72	.964	Strongly Agree	Very High
33 The lines and methods of communication between teachers and the principal in our school are well developed and maintained.	3.22	.872	Agree	High
35 Our principal promotes a sense of belonging among the teachers in our school.	3.33	.121	Agree	High
45 My principal is concerned with the problems of the faculty and handles these problems sympathetically.	2.98	.606	Agree	High
46 I do not hesitate to discuss any school problem with my principal.	3.1	.923	Agree	High
Satisfaction with Teaching	Mean	SD	Verbal Description	Interpretation
17 Teaching gives me a great deal of personal satisfaction.	3.13	.523	Agree	High
22 Teaching enables me to make my greatest contribution to society.	3.13	.523	Agree	High
23 I love to teach.	3.24	.864	Agree	High
24 If I could plan my career again, I would choose teaching.	2.64	.772	Agree	High
25 I would recommend teaching as an occupation to students of high scholastic ability.	2.98	.921	Agree	High
26 If I could earn as much money in another occupation, I would stop teaching.	1.17	.506	Strongly Disagree	Very Low
37 I feel that I am an important part of this school system.	2.47	.823	Disagree	Low
40 I feel successful and competent in my present position.	3.3	.664	Agree	High
42 I am at a disadvantage professionally because other teachers are better prepared to teach than I am.	2.26	.972	Disagree	Low
43 As far as I know, the other teachers think I am a good teacher.	3.11	.521	Agree	High
44 The "stress and strain" resulting from teaching makes teaching undesirable for me.	3	.606	Agree	High
50 I am well satisfied with my present teaching position.	3.19	.523	Agree	High
Rapport Among Teachers	Mean	SD	Verbal Description	Interpretation
16 There is a great deal of griping, arguing, taking sides and feuding among our teachers.	3.24	.723	Agree	High
20 Generally, teachers in our school do not take advantage of one another.	3.13	.664	Agree	High
21 The teachers in our school cooperate with each other to achieve common, personal, and professional objectives.	3.19	.572	Agree	High
38 The competency of the teachers in our school compares favorably with that of teachers in other schools in which I am familiar.	2.96	.321	Agree	High
41 The teachers in our school work well together.	3.51	.406	Strongly Agree	Very High
Teacher Salary	Mean	SD	Verbal Description	Interpretation
7. I am satisfied with the policies under which pay raises are granted	2.94	0.00	Disagree	Low
Teacher Load	Mean	SD	Verbal Description	Interpretation
4 Teachers in this school are expected to do an unreasonable amount of record keeping and clerical work.	1.85	.423	Disagree	Low
6 Community demands upon the teacher's time are unreasonable.	1.96	.864	Disagree	Low
8 My teaching load is greater than that of most of the other teachers in our school.	2.74	.472	Agree	High
9 The extra-curricular load of the teachers in our school is unreasonable.	2.17	.321	Disagree	Low
12 The number of hours a teacher must work is unreasonable.	2	.406	Disagree	Low
28 Keeping up professionally is too much of a burden.	2.32	.523	Disagree	Low
32 My classes are used as "dumping grounds" for problem students.	2.52	.564	Agree	High
34 My teaching load at this school is unreasonable.	1.77	.672	Disagree	Low
36 My teaching load unduly restricts my nonprofessional activities.	1.51	.721	Disagree	Low
Curriculum Issues	Mean	SD	Verbal Description	Interpretation
15 Our school has a well-balanced curriculum.	3.42	.423	Agree	High
18 The curriculum of our school makes reasonable provision for student individual differences.	3.72	.564	Strongly Agree	Very High
Teacher status	Mean	SD	Verbal Description	Interpretation
11 My teaching position gives me the social status in the community that I desire.	3.54	.223	Strongly Agree	Very High

13 Teaching enables me to enjoy many of the material and cultural things I like.	3.16	.364	Strongly Agree	High
29 Our community makes its teachers feel as though they are a real part of the community.	3.86	.172	Strongly Agree	Very High
30 Teaching affords me the security I want in an occupation.	3.38	.121	Agree	High
47 Teaching gives me the prestige I desire.	3.3	.106	Agree	High
48 My teaching job enables me to provide a satisfactory standard of living for my family.	3.5	.223	Strongly Agree	High
School Facilities and Services	Mean	SD	Verbal Description	Interpretation
14 My school provides me with adequate classroom supplies and equipment.	2.09	.158	Disagree	Low
19 The procedures for obtaining materials and services are well defined and efficient.	2.42	.223	Disagree	Low
39 My school provides the teachers with adequate audio - visual aids and projection equipment.	1.27	.364	Strongly Agree	Very Low

Table 6. Summary of Morale Satisfaction of Teachers Along with the Following Factors Namely Teacher Rapport with School Head, Satisfaction with Teaching, Rapport Among Teachers, Teacher Salary, Teacher Load, Curriculum Issues, Teacher Status, and School Facilities

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description	Interpretation
1 Teacher Rapport with School Head	3.11	.550	Agree	High
2 Satisfaction with Teaching	2.80	.543	Agree	High
3 Rapport among Teachers	3.2	.087	Agree	High
4 Teacher Salary	2.94	.289	Agree	High
5 Teacher Load	2.09	.114	Strongly Disagree	Low
6 Curriculum Issues	3.57	.158	Strongly Agree	Very High
7 Teacher Status	3.45	.223	Agree	High
8 School Facilities and Services	1.92	.364	Strongly Disagree	Low
Overall Mean	2.85	.290	Agree	High

Legend: 4.50-5.00, Always, Very High; 3.50-4.49, Often, High; 2.50-3.49, Sometimes, Moderate; 1.50-2.49, Seldom, Low; 1.00-1.49, Never, Very Low

Table 6 presents the summary of morale satisfaction along with the following factors namely teacher rapport with school head, satisfaction with teaching, rapport among teachers, teacher salary, teacher load, curriculum issues, teacher status, and school facilities. As shown in the table, the teachers have higher assessment in indicator number 6 “curriculum issues” with a mean of 3.57, followed by indicator number 7 “teacher status” with a mean of 3.45, and indicator number 3 “rapport among teachers” with a mean of 3.20. Meanwhile, On the other hand, teachers obtained lower assessments in indicator number 8 “school facilities and services” with a lowest mean of 1.92, followed by indicator number 5 “teacher load” with a mean of 2.09, and indicator number 2 “satisfaction with teaching” with a mean of 2.80. The overall mean is 2.85 which can be inferred that the teachers have higher level of morale satisfaction.

Griffiths (2016) wrote that good teacher morale depends on acceptance and recognition of group goals and that the group must actively resist whatever interferes with the attainment of their goals. Van Zwoll (2014) contended that morale cannot be created or guaranteed. He also expressed the idea that the most that can be done is to create conditions which favor good morale and remedy conditions that threaten good morale.

The attitudes may be favorable or destructive. Either attitude can be looked on as an indicator of morale. Even unfavorable feelings toward an organization can indicate that the employee has a true interest in the success of the organization (Fawcett, 2004).

Bentley and Rempel (2008) used the Purdue Teacher Opinionnaire to measure the morale of 3,075 teachers in Indiana and Oregon. Not only did they measure the differences in morale, but they also identified the elements responsible for the differences. Their findings indicated that differences in teacher morale were attributed to such factors as salary, age, and status. Hopefully the present study will help to verify the findings of Bentley and Rempel's study.

Magoon and Linkous (2009) stressed that there is a need for further review of the existing literature on the subject of teacher morale and especially the factors that affect morale. Findings of the present study will hopefully be used by administrators and educational researchers so that they may be better informed as to the relationship between teacher morale and administrative leadership styles and, perhaps, examine their own educational programs in relation to these findings.

Problem 4. What is the teachers' performance in school based on the Performance Appraisal System for Teachers (PAST) in terms of Instructional Competence, Professional and Personal Characteristics, and Punctuality and Attendance?

Table 7 presents the level of teachers' performance in school based on the Performance Appraisal System for Teachers (PAST) in terms of Instructional Competence, Professional and Personal Characteristics, and Punctuality and Attendance. As shown in the table, the lowest score obtained for PAST is 3.0 and the highest score obtained is 5.0. Of the three criteria of PAST, the teachers have obtained highest mean in instructional competence with a mean of 3.87, followed by punctuality and attendance with a mean of 3.74. Meanwhile,

the teachers obtained a lower mean in professional and personal characteristics with a mean of 3.59. The overall mean is 3.73 which can be interpreted that the teachers have performed very satisfactory in their school works.

Table 7. *Level of Teachers' Performance in School Based on the Performance Appraisal System for Teachers (PAST) in terms of Instructional Competence, Professional and Personal Characteristics, and Punctuality and Attendance*

PAST Indicators	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Instructional Competence	150	3.0	5.0	3.87	0.55	Very Satisfactory
Professional and Personal Characteristics	150	3.0	5.0	3.59	0.68	Very Satisfactory
Punctuality and Attendance	150	3.0	5.0	3.74	0.63	Very Satisfactory
Overall Mean				3.73	0.62	Very Satisfactory

Legend: 4.50-5.00, Always, Very High; 3.50-4.49, Often, High; 2.50-3.49, Sometimes, Moderate; 1.50-2.49, Seldom, Low; 1.00-1.49, Never, Very Low

In 2011, Smith and Westen defined morale as "...an attitude of satisfaction with desire to continue in, and willingness to strive for the goals of a particular group organization" Guba and Qidwell suggested that morale as it concernsthe teacher is the interaction and relationships among role-expectations, needs-dispositions, and institutional goals. Hoeke in 1959, refactor analyzed a previous study of multiple-choice and sentence completion morale scores andfound four factors which were common to both types of measurement, This study utilized Air Force personnel.

More recent studies of teacher morale have indicated that there is agreement among researchers in education and psychology that teacher morale is multidimensional. In 2007, Coffman attempted to relate teacher morale with participation in curriculum development and found that morale is the result of "litttle" things.

Problem 5. Is there a significant relationship between teachers' performance, transformational leadership practices of school heads assessed by teachers, transformational leadership assessment of school heads, and morale satisfaction of teachers?

Table 8. *Pearson r Analyses for Significant Relationship Between Teachers' Performance, Transformational Leadership Practices of School Heads Assessed by Teachers, Transformational Leadership Assessment of School Heads, and Morales Satisfaction of Teachers*

Dependent Variable	Independent Variable	N	R	Interpretation	Sig. (P-value)
Teachers' Performance	Morale Satisfaction	0.70	0.039	0.70	Significant
	Transformational Leadership of Teachers	0.85	0.020	0.85	Significant
	Transformational Leadership of School Heads	0.19	0.268	0.19	Not Significant

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 8 presents the Pearson r analyses for significant relationship between teachers' performance, transformational leadership practices of school heads assessed by teachers, transformational leadership assessment of school heads, and morale satisfaction of teachers. As shown in the table, the P-values for morale satisfaction and teacher's transformational leadership are lesser than the level of significance of 0.05 which indicate that there is a strong positive significant relationship between the teacher's performance and the said independent variables. This implied that increasing these variables would also increase the teachers' PAST performance. Likewise, the P-value of the transformational leadership of school heads is greater than the significance level of 0.05 which means that it has no direct correlation to teachers' PAST performance.

Leech and Fulton (2002) studied the differences in the perceptions of middle and high school teachers in relationship to the leadership practices of their educational leaders. The sample population consisted of 242 teachers from 12 middle schools and 404 teachers from 14 high schools. All participants were teachers in a large urban school district. Teachers completed Kouzes and Posner's (1995) Leadership Practices Inventory. The authors found there was no significant difference between middle and high school teachers' perceptions of their principals' leadership practices. eachers at both levels rated their principals highest in the leadership practices of enabling others to act and modeling the way. They rated their principals as least demonstrating the leadership practice of encouraging the heart.

Lucas and Valentine (2002) attempted to determine if there was any directrelationship between a principals' transformational leadership and school team transformational leadership, transformational leadership and school culture, school team transformational leadership and school culture, and if school team transformational eadership either moderates or mediates the relationship between principal transformational leadership behavior and school culture.

Piles, Johnson, Brooks, and Jacobson (2005) noted the lack of research regarding successful leadership practices in relationship to the urban school setting. A multi-perspective case study methodology was used to avoid the limitation of a self-report study. One elementary school principal from a once failing school was the target of the study. Results indicated that transformational leadership behaviors positively impacted school change in a failing urban school. The behaviors of support, care, trust, participation, facilitation, and the building of consensus were reported as leadership characteristics of the principal. It was also stated that the principal focused on long-term, substantial change issues, as opposed to more administrative responsibilities.

Problem 6. Which from the independent variables best predict teachers' performance?

Table 9. Summary of Multiple Regression Analyses for Variables Predicting Teachers' Performance of the Elementary School Teachers

Variable	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	P-value	Interpretation
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
(Constant)	2.807	0.706		3.97	0.00	
Transformational Leadership of School Heads	0.147	0.127	0.196	1.157	0.249	Not Significant
Transformational Leadership of Teachers	1.10	0.079	0.104	1.26	0.021	Significant
Moral Factors Satisfaction	1.49	0.057	0.271	0.855	0.039	Significant
R = 0.50	R ² = 0.23		Adjusted R ² =0.20	F=1.12	Sig.=0.008	

Dependent Variable: Teachers' Performance

Table 9 presents the Summary of Multiple Regression Analyses for Variables Predicting Teachers' Performance. The R value of 0.50 indicates moderate positive correlation between the independent variables and the teachers' performance. The R² value of 0.23 indicates that the variables explain 23% of the variability of the teachers' performance. Meanwhile, the P-value of 0.008 implies that there is a no significant relationship between the independent variables and the teachers' performance in general. Furthermore, the regression output above shows that the best predictor variable is moral factors satisfaction of teachers followed by transformational leadership of teachers while the transformational leadership of school heads failed to predict the teachers' performance. Based on the B coefficients values, the regression equation is $Y=2.807 + 1.49 + 1.10$. The equation implies that for every point increase of moral factors satisfaction of teachers, there is a corresponding 1.49 PAST increase, and for every point increase of teachers' transformational leadership, there is a corresponding 1.1 PAST increase.

According to Mitchell and Crawford (1995), "performance assessment is the measure of whether or not and to what degree students achieve the standards" (p. 78). Similarly, Edmonstone (1996) equates performance assessment to enhanced communication of standards and objectives, clarification of individual responsibilities and accountabilities, and a definition and measurement of individual performance practice. In education, performance standards are most often measured by way of rubrics that indicate opportunities for growth, self reflection, and areas of strength and/or improvement (Bartlett, 2002). example, Mitchell et al. (2001) note a lack of empirical evidence supporting the effectiveness of licensing tests in predicting effective classroom teaching.

Further, tests administered by Faculties of Education often vary between programs, instructors, and institutions, and, as such, they rarely provide data that can be accurately and effectively analyzed and compared (Pecheone and Chung (2006)).

According to Pecheone and Chung, performance assessments that include evidence observed during actual teaching practices provide more direct evaluation of teaching ability.

Federal Higher Education Act requires that "schools of education be evaluated based on graduates' performance on licensing tests" (Darling-Hammond, 2006)

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the study concluded that the school teachers perceived their school heads with high level of transformational leadership. The school heads have high level of transformational leadership. The school teachers have high level of moral satisfaction in dealing with personal and professional school activities. The elementary school teachers have higher rating in their Performance appraisal indicating that they better classroom teaching performance. The elementary school teachers' Performance appraisal has a significant relationship to the teachers' transformational leadership assessment and teachers' morale satisfaction while it has no significant relationship to school heads transformational leadership, and Teachers' morale satisfaction is the best predictor to teachers' performance, which implies that once teachers are satisfied of their personal and professional engagement in the school, their performance would be better.

Based on the conclusions, the study came up with the following recommendations:

The DepEd Division officials of Lanao del Sur may conduct regular seminar on transformational leadership especially to the newly appointed school heads.

The school heads are encouraged to conduct a school-based training on transformational leadership to the school teachers.

The DepEd Division of Lanao del Sur may consider allocating additional budget for the purchase of school facilities and for the improvement of the school services.

The DepEd division officials of Lanao del Sur may require school teachers to undergo transformational leadership before they can be appointed as school heads.

Another study may be conducted to include other school heads and school teachers from other DepEd divisions to confirm the findings

of this study.

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